

Water-efficient management strategies in rice production

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Food security in Asia is challenged by increasing food demand and threatened by declining water availability. Rice is the most important staple in Asia, where it provides 35–80% of total calorie intake (IRRI 1997). More than 75% of the rice supply comes from 79 million ha of irrigated land. Thus, Asia's present and future food security depends largely on the irrigated rice production system. However, the water-use efficiency of rice is low, and growing rice requires large amounts of water. In Asia, irrigated agriculture accounts for 90% of total diverted freshwater, and more than 50% of this is used to irrigate rice. Until recently, this amount of water has been taken for granted, but now the global "water crisis" threatens the sustainability of irrigated rice production. The available amount of water for irrigation is becoming scarce (Gleick 1993, Postel 1997). The reasons for this are diverse and location-specific, but include decreasing quality (chemical pollution, salinization), decreasing resources (e.g., falling groundwater tables, silting of reservoirs), and increased competition from other sectors such as urban and industrial users. Because of the increasing scarcity of water, the costs of its use and resource development are increasing as well. Therefore, farmers and researchers alike are looking for ways to decrease water use in rice production and increase its use efficiency. A fundamental approach is to start at the field level, where water and rice interact. For farmers with no control over the availability or distribution of water beyond their farm gates, the crucial question to be addressed is "What are the options to cope with decreasing water supply (or the increasing costs of it) at the farm or field inlets?" To answer this question,

we have to look at the flow of water in rice fields and understand where reductions in water use can be achieved without impairing yield (Fig. 1).

Rice and water input

Irrigated lowland rice in Asia is transplanted or direct (wet) seeded into puddled lowland fields. Land preparation consists of soaking, plowing, and puddling. Puddling is done not only to control weed, but also to increase water retention, reduce soil permeability, and ease field leveling and transplanting (De Datta 1981). Soaking, a one-time operation, requires water to bring the topsoil to saturation and to create a ponded water layer. After land preparation, there is an "idle period" until transplanting or direct seeding takes place. The growth period runs from crop establishment to harvest. During the idle period and crop growth, fields are typically flooded with 5–10 cm of water. Under flooded conditions, water is required to match several outflow processes. Because of the standing water, hydrostatic pressure continuously "pushes" water downward through the puddled layer. When this water flows vertically downward below the root zone, it is called percolation (P), and, when it flows laterally underneath bunds, it is called seepage (S). Because they are difficult to separate in the field, S and P are of-

ten taken together as one term: SP. Water is released into the air by evaporation (E) from the ponded water layer and transpiration (T) by the crop. Again, E and T are difficult to separate in the field and they are mostly considered together as evapotranspiration (ET). However, during land preparation and the idle period, only E takes place, whereas, during crop growth, both E and T occur. Finally, over-bund flow (or surface runoff) is the spillover when water depths rise above the field bunds.

Table 1 gives typical values of water outflows from a rice field. For a crop growth duration of 100 d (typical of modern high-yielding varieties), total water requirements vary from 675 to 4,450 mm, depending on the season and soil characteristics, with 1,500–2,000 mm as a typical value in many lowland areas. Of all outflows of water from a rice field, only

Table 1. Typical daily and seasonal rates of water use in rice production in the tropics.

Item	Daily (mm d ⁻¹)	Seasonal (mm)
Land preparation	–	175–750
Evapotranspiration		
Wet season	4–5	400–500
Dry season	6–7	600–700
Seepage and percolation		
Heavy clays	1–5	100–500
Loamy/sandy soils	25–30	2,500–3,000

Fig. 1. Components of the water balance of a rice field.

It is “productive” water use as it leads directly to crop growth and yield formation. Transpiration is essential to crop growth because it provides cooling and is the driving process for water flow in plants that carries nutrients from the roots to the shoot. Most of the water use in rice, however, is caused by large losses of seepage and percolation. These flows are unproductive as they do not contribute to crop growth and yield formation.

Water management strategies to reduce water input

Large reductions in water input can potentially be realized by reducing the unproductive SP flows during crop growth and idle periods (Bouman and Tuong 2001). There are basically two ways to do so: (1) increasing the resistance to water flow in the soil and (2) decreasing the hydrostatic pressure (i.e., depth) of the ponded water. The resistance to water flow can be increased by changing the soil physical properties. Cabangon and Tuong (2000) have shown the beneficial effects of an additional shallow soil tillage before land preparation to close cracks that cause rapid bypass flow at land soaking. Thorough puddling results in a good compacted plow soil that impedes vertical water flow (De Datta 1981). Soil compaction using heavy machinery can decrease soil permeability in certain coarse-textured soil types (Harnpichitvitaya et al 2001). Finally, researchers have even experimented with introducing physical barriers underneath rice soils such as bitumen layers and plastic sheets

(Garrity et al 1992). However, effective, though, most of these soil improvements are expensive and beyond the financial means of farmers.

Reducing SP flows through reduced hydrostatic pressure can be achieved by water management. Instead of keeping the rice field continuously flooded with 5–10 cm of water, the floodwater depth can be decreased, the soil can be kept around saturation (saturated soil culture [SSC]), or alternate wetting and drying (AWD) regimes can be imposed. Under these management practices, the hydrology of the soil changes from anaerobic under flooded and SSC regimes to alternately anaerobic and aerobic under AWD. Ultimately, rice could be grown under completely aerobic conditions and continuous SP eliminated (Table 2). These water management technologies are reviewed in more detail below.

Saturated soil culture and alternate wetting and drying

Bouman and Tuong (2001) compiled a database on SSC and AWD from IRRI experiments and those reported in the literature. The database contains information from 31 pot and field experiments undertaken in north and central India, the Philippines, and Japan. In SSC, the soil is kept as close to saturation as possible. This mostly means that shallow irrigation is given to obtain about 1-cm floodwater depth a day or so after the disappearance of standing water. In AWD, irrigation water is applied to obtain 2–5-cm floodwater depth after a certain number of days after the disappearance of ponded wa-

Table 2. Classification of rice production systems by water management strategies.

	Flooded lowland				Dryland	
			Lowland (anaerobic)		Aerobic	
Characteristic	Conventional flooded	Saturated soil culture	Alternate wetting and drying		Aerobic rice	Upland rice
			Irrigated	Rainfed		
Hydrology	Flooded	Saturation	Flooded ↔ aerobic	Flooded ↔ aerobic	Aerobic	Aerobic
Irrigation	Irrigated	Irrigated	Irrigated	Rainfed	Irrigated, rainfed	Rainfed
Tillage	Puddled, nonpuddled, Bunded	Puddled, nonpuddled, Bunded	Puddled, nonpuddled, Bunded	Puddled, nonpuddled, Bunded	Nonpuddled, Bunded	Nonpuddled, Nonbunded?
Environment	Favorable lowland	Favorable lowland	Favorable lowland	Unfavorable lowland	Favorable upland, unfavorable lowland	Unfavorable upland
Germplasm	Lowland	Lowland	Lowland	Lowland	Improved upland × lowland	Upland
Yield level	High	High	High-medium	Medium-low	High-medium	Low

ter. In 92% of the cases investigated by Bouman and Tuong (2001), SSC and AWD resulted in decreased water input, but at the expense of decreased yield. The SSC practice was most efficient in decreasing water use: input reductions ranged from 5% to 50% and averaged 23%. However, reducing floodwater depth to just-saturated levels already reduced yields by 0–12%, with an average of 6%. Implementing SSC requires good water control at the field level and frequent shallow irrigations that are labor-intensive. Borell et al (1997) experimented with raised bed systems in Australia to ease SSC practices. Their beds were 120 cm wide, separated by furrows of 30-cm width and 15-cm depth. Near-continuous irrigation through the furrows kept beds saturated. Compared with flooded rice, water savings were 34% and yield losses 16–34%.

AWD practices resulted in both water savings and yield losses of 0–70% compared with flooded treatments, depending on the number of days between irrigations and existing soil conditions. Mostly, however, yield losses were smaller than reductions in water input, and water productivities therefore increased. There is a trade-off between land productivity (i.e., yield) and water productivity. Figure 2 shows the so-called water production functions for two examples of AWD field experiments in India and closed pot experiments in growth chambers in Japan. The lowest curve line is from Indian experiments in soils with SP rates of 21 mm d⁻¹, low N inputs (80 kg ha⁻¹), and zero P and K (Jha et al 1981). On the right-hand side of the curve are data on continuously flooded treatments. Going to the left are the first AWD treatments that reduced SP with no effect on yield levels. The crop was probably able to satisfy its transpiration requirements or the low nutrient level was more yield-limiting than water. Further to the left are data on more severe AWD treatments, where yields dropped when crop water consumption decreased. The second higher curve is also from Indian experiments, but with lower SP rates (9–14 mm d⁻¹) and higher nutrient inputs (120 kg N ha⁻¹, 26.4 kg P ha⁻¹, and 33.2 kg K ha⁻¹) (Tripathi et al 1986). From right to left on this curve, yields dropped faster than in the other experiment in India since water quickly became yield-limiting. Both Indian production curves illustrate the law of diminishing returns to water input. Water productivities were highest on the left side of the curves, where water was the most limiting growth factor, but where yield levels were low. Data on the straight line are from closed pot experiments in Japan (Anbumozhi et al 1998). Since closed

pots have no SP losses, reductions in water input immediately affected ET; consequently, yields declined steeply. These data represent the absolute minimum water use by rice and the highest water productivities that can be realized. The challenge in developing water-efficient rice production systems is to reduce water inputs while maintaining yields at the same high level as that under flooded conditions. In Figure 2, that means going on a straight line along the top of the production curves of the field experiments from the right to the left until the straight line of the pot experiments is reached (as indicated by arrows).

Aerobic rice

A fundamental approach to reduce water inputs in rice is to grow the crop like an irrigated upland crop such as wheat or maize. Instead of trying to reduce water input in lowland fields, the concept of having the field flooded or saturated is abandoned altogether. Upland crops are grown in nonpuddled aerobic soil without standing water. Irrigation is applied to bring the soil water content in the root zone up to field capacity after it has reached a certain lower threshold (e.g., halfway between field capacity and wilting point). The amount of irrigation water should match evaporation from the soil and transpiration by the crop. Since it is not possible to apply irrigation water to the root zone only, some of it is lost by deep percolation and is unavailable for uptake by the crop. Typical field application efficiencies vary from 60–70% using surface irrigation (e.g., flash or furrow irrigation) to more than 90% using sprinkler or drip irrigation. The

Fig. 2. Yield vs water input. Data from field experiments in India by Jha et al (1981) (◇) and Tripathi et al (1986) (◆), and in Japan by Anbumozhi et al (1998) (○). The arrows indicate the ideal line for water savings while maintaining high yields. Source: Bouman and Tuong (2001).

potential water savings when rice can be grown as an irrigated upland crop are large, especially on soils with high SP rates. Besides cutting down on SP losses, evaporation can also be reduced with this technique since there is no continuous standing water layer.

De Datta et al (1973) tried growing rice like an upland crop using furrow irrigation in the 1971 dry season at IRRI. Using the high-yielding lowland variety IR20, total water (irrigation plus rainfall) savings were 56% and irrigation water savings 78% compared with growing the crop under flooded conditions. However, yield decreased from 7.9 to 3.4 t ha⁻¹. Upland cultivars that performed equally well under flooded and dryland irrigation were used, but their yields of around 5 t ha⁻¹ were much lower than those of lowland cultivars.

Studies on nonflooded irrigated rice using sprinkler irrigation were conducted in the United States in Texas and Louisiana (McCauley 1990, Westcott and Vines 1986). Experiments used commercial rice cultivars under lowland cultivation. Irrigation water requirements were 20–50% less than in flooded rice, depending on soil type, rainfall, and water management. The highest yielding cultivars (producing 7–8 t ha⁻¹ under flooded conditions), however, had yield reductions of 20–30% compared with flooded rice. The most drought-resistant cultivars produced the same under both conditions, but their yields were much lower (5–6 t ha⁻¹). Under economic conditions prevalent in the US, the adoption of irrigated dryland rice (using existing cultivars) was not economically attractive.

New varieties must be developed if growing rice like an irrigated upland crop is to be successful. Lowland cultivars have been selected to give high yields under continuously flooded lowland conditions. They generally suffer a yield loss when the soil water content drops below saturation (see above). Upland varieties have been developed to give stable though low yields in adverse environments where rainfall is low, irrigation is absent, soils are poor or toxic, weed pressure is high, and farmers are too poor to supply high inputs. Therefore, IRRI recently coined the term “aerobic rice” to refer to high-yielding rice grown in nonpuddled aerobic soil. This aerobic rice, which can be rainfed or irrigated, should be responsive to high inputs and should tolerate flooding. It has to combine characteristics of both upland and high-yielding lowland varieties. Evidence for the feasibility of aerobic rice comes from Brazil and north China. In Brazil, aero-

bic rice cultivars have come out of a 20-year breeding program to improve upland rice with yields of 5–7 t ha⁻¹ under sprinkler irrigation in farmers’ fields (Silveira Pinheiro and Maia de Castro, pers. commun.). These varieties are grown commercially on 250,000 ha in the state of Mato Grosso. In north China, aerobic rice cultivars yield up to 6–7.5 t ha⁻¹ in farmers’ fields using flash irrigation in bunded fields (Wang and Tang 2000). It is estimated that these cultivars are now being grown on some 120,000 ha in the north China plains. Field visits in 2000–01 revealed that farmers have pioneered this system in different environments:

- Where rainfall is insufficient to sustain lowland rice production (estimated to require 1,200–1,500 mm) but thought to be sufficient for aerobic rice (estimated to require some 800 mm). Here, maize is the dominant crop and rice is an attractive alternative through the benefits of crop diversification. Moreover, the price of rice is supported by the government, and farmers perceive this as advantageous.
- In pump-irrigated areas where water has become so expensive that lowland rice production was abandoned.
- Where water is scarce during the first part of the growing season (necessitating irrigation), but floods occur in the second part. Upland crops such as maize and soybean cannot withstand flooding, but aerobic rice can.

In both Brazil and China, however, it has been reported that high initial yields are difficult to sustain and that yields may decline severely after 3–4 years of continuous cropping. Brazil has adopted a rotation system in which aerobic rice is only cropped once every 3–4 years. The causes for the yield decline are not yet understood, but likely candidates are the buildup of soil-borne diseases (such as nematodes) or toxic substances.

Discussion and conclusions

Water in irrigated rice production has been taken for granted for centuries, but the “looming water crisis” may change the way rice is produced in the future. Water-saving irrigation technologies that were investigated in the early 1970s, such as saturated soil culture and alternate wetting and drying, are receiving renewed attention from researchers. These technologies reduce water input, though mostly at the expense of some yield loss. Farmers

in Asia who confront scarcity or high costs of water have already started to adopt these technologies. In China, various forms of AWD and reduced flood-water depths have been developed and massively adopted by farmers (Li 2001). Surveys in north-central India (A.K. Singh, pers. commun.) and in Central Luzon, Philippines (unpublished IRRI data), show that farmers who operate pumps to irrigate their fields consciously apply some form of AWD to save on energy costs.

Aerobic rice is a new concept to further decrease water requirements in rice production. It is commercially grown in Brazil and is being pioneered by farmers in northern China. In the heart of the rice-wheat belt in India (Haryana, the Punjab, and Uttar Pradesh), innovative farmers have begun to grow rice aerobically under furrow irrigation in raised-bed systems (personal field observations). Changes in the hydrology of rice production will have major consequences for its sustainability and appropriate management practices. Over the centuries, lowland rice has proven to be a remarkably sustainable system, mostly because of its particular anaerobic character. Water-saving irrigation practices shift away from continuous anaerobic conditions to alternate anaerobic-aerobic and continuous aerobic conditions. Table 2 lists water management strategies in rice production and summarizes some key characteristics. The shift from anaerobic to aerobic systems will have major consequences for weed, disease, and insect pest management, nutrient and soil organic matter dynamics, and greenhouse gas emission and sequestration. Weed control is an especially crucial issue in most water-saving irrigation technologies. Water has long been the cheapest herbicide, but this may not be so any more in the near future. Breeders have to respond to the challenge of breeding varieties that perform well under nonpermanently flooded conditions. The development of aerobic rice varieties is probably the most ambitious challenge of all.

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